

Sustainability in Social Entrepreneurship: Using a PRISMA Approach to Understand Poverty Reduction and Inequality Interventions in Emerging Economies

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Abstract

Background: Emerging economies, often characterised by significant social and economic disparities, provide a critical context for examining how social entrepreneurs can drive sustainable development to reduce poverty and inequality. It has been identified that developing countries are facing numerous problems, especially economic, social, and bio-environmental problems, such as income disparity, unequal access to education, unemployment, information asymmetry, and corruption.

Objective: This study aims to investigate the role of social entrepreneurship in eradicating poverty and inequality in emerging economies, such as Sub-Saharan Africa.

Methodology: This study employed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) approach to investigate sustainability in social entrepreneurship in poverty and inequality intervention in emerging countries. Studies were selected through identification, screening, eligibility, and analysis.

Results: The findings underscore the potential of social entrepreneurship to contribute significantly to sustainable development goals by fostering inclusive growth and reducing disparities in areas of poverty and inequality in emerging economies.

Conclusion: Sustainable social entrepreneurship has transformed emerging economies by accelerating transformation, promoting social justice, and ensuring that growth benefits all members of society.

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Unique contribution: The study could be useful to researchers, practitioners, social entrepreneurs, and governments in making strategic investment decisions and overcoming challenges in poverty and inequity.

Key Recommendation: Social entrepreneurs should collaborate with governments, commercial businesses, and community members to garner support and achieve lasting results in solving the problem of poverty and inequality in developing nations.

Keywords: Social Entrepreneurship, Poverty, Inequality, Sustainability, Sustainable Development Goal (SDG1 and 10), Emerging Economies.

Introduction

Poverty and inequality have increased over the last years due to unemployment, corruption, non-diversification of the economy, income disparity, poor learning system, flooding and a lack of basic facilities. Elimination of poverty and inequalities is an essential agenda towards sustainable development in emerging economies. Emerging economies have characteristics of high economic growth rates, industrialisation, and urbanisation, which are associated with large social disparities. In many of these nations, a considerable part of the population lives in poverty, and economic disparity is high (Delgado et al., 2024). Traditional measures for poverty alleviation and inequality reduction, such as government initiatives and foreign aid, have needed better effectiveness in attaining long-term objectives. According to the World Bank (2022), more than 40% of Nigerians live below the poverty line. This widespread poverty is exacerbated by substantial disparities in economic distribution, education, healthcare, and other basic amenities. The World Bank states that the poverty rate in Nigeria will increase by 46% in 2024, representing 104 million poor Nigerians (Yeboua et al., 2022). This rate has remained one of the reasons why Nigeria has not made impressive progress towards the achievement of sustainable development. In Rural areas, the poverty level stands at about 52%, while in urban areas, the percentage is about 18%. It is pertinent to NOTE that the northern part of Nigeria, and particularly the North East and North West, has the highest poverty levels. Sokoto, Taraba and Jigawa, for instance, were seen to have poverty headcounts of over 80%. The Gini coefficient for Nigeria is roughly 35.1 as per the data of 2018, which demonstrates a moderate level of income inequality. The richest quintile controls more than half of the nation's income, while the lowest quintile controls less than 5%. This has been a major challenge, penetrating many emerging economies such as Nigeria, which has hampered the realisation of sustainable development. The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 1 (No Poverty) and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities), have further emphasised the importance of innovative approaches to addressing these challenges.

Social entrepreneurship has gained increased attention as an innovative approach to solving problems that affect society, particularly in emerging economies where poverty and inequity are rampant hindrances to development (Alao & Alao, 2021). Amid poverty and social inequality, new opportunities for social change, social entrepreneurship, have appeared and reveal a great potential for transformation in the nation's socioeconomic relations (Ogbari, Folorunso, Simon-Ilogho, Adebayo, Olanrewaju, Efegbudu, & Omoregbe, 2024). Social entrepreneurship is more than just business and community development to make profits; it tackles problems and encourages sustainability. In fact, many of the traditional development models have been unable to offer effective and sustainable solutions for these problems. Social entrepreneurship, however, entails a shift from conventional business thinking coupled with social responsibility (Arejiogbe,

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Moses, Salau, Onayemi, Agada, Dada & Obisesan, 2023). Social entrepreneurs are predisposed to solve problems such as poverty and unequal distribution of resources. Social entrepreneurship contributes to the introduction of sustainable business initiatives and organisational models that correspond to the objectives of the International Development Cooperation. Many researchers and practitioners have argued that social entrepreneurship can be used in eradicating poverty and inequality in needy and low-income parts of the globe (Lubberink, 2020; Gupta & Srivastava, 2021). According to Iyortsuun (2016), social entrepreneurship has received immeasurable attention. However, there has been an absence of scholarly research that explores the efficiency of social entrepreneurship in fighting poverty and inequality in developing countries like Nigeria.

Social entrepreneurship contributes significantly to economic growth through employment creation, economic diversification and the generation of new entrepreneurs. In nations such as Nigeria, high levels of unemployment and underemployment are some of the challenges being experienced, and this is where social entrepreneurship has the opportunity to diversify the economy and empower the youth, as well as women (Gupta & Srivastava, 2021). These contributions not only fight poverty but also spearhead stability and cohesion in society. The significance of this review extends not only to theoretical implications but also to practical implications in real-world practice. Given that governments, international organisations and companies' stakeholders are realising the benefits of social entrepreneurship in solving development issues, it is essential to understand the antecedents of sustainable impact. Such information can help in identifying the right strategies or directions to undertake in order to assist these social entrepreneurs to realize their visions and bring positive change in the emerging economies.

The sustainability of social entrepreneurship, especially in poverty reduction and inequality reduction in emerging economies, has garnered significant attention over time. There is a growing need to come up with practical solutions that can effectively respond to informed global inequalities and escalating social and economic challenges. The PRISMA approach of Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses provides a clear and systematic way to plan, conduct and summarize the literature on the effects of social entrepreneurship on poverty and inequality in these areas at a glance. In this extensive review, the author discusses the diverse aspects of sustainability in social entrepreneurship, enhanced by the finding that such entrepreneurship may significantly lessen poverty and inequality in emerging economies. This research is referenced in relation to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 1 and 10). However, the study aims to investigate the role of social entrepreneurship in eradicating poverty and inequality in emerging economies, such as Nigeria. The following research objectives were provided to be addressed in this study.

Research Objective

The general objective of this study is to examine the role of social entrepreneurship in eradicating poverty and inequality in emerging economies like Nigeria using Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA). The specific objectives to be addressed in this study is as follows;

- To ascertain the influence of social entrepreneurship on poverty and inequality reduction.
- To identify social entrepreneurs' barriers to implementing poverty reduction and inequality intervention strategies.

Literature Review: Overview of Entrepreneurship

Like every other subject or discipline, entrepreneurship has no generally accepted definition (Arejiogbe *et al.*, 2023). Entrepreneurship is faced with economic challenges, and most countries hope to achieve a complete advantage through creativity and revitalize the economy by promoting entrepreneurship. The concept of entrepreneurship is seen from the functional resources and the psychological and behavioural perspectives. van der Westhuizen and Adalakun (2023) say entrepreneurship is the readiness and the capacity of a business disapproved of people to distinguish the territories of necessities of individuals, search for assets to coordinate these requirements, consolidate these assets in an ideal manner, bear the un-insurable hazard and built up a fruitful and beneficial endeavour. Creating new ideas, transforming those ideas into profitable businesses, using innovative practices, and producing work are among the many values entrepreneurs worldwide have followed. Entrepreneurship can be a process that involves a person or individual's effort to identify sustainable business opportunities (Dada, Adegbuyi, & Ogbari, 2023). Both general and social entrepreneurship are crucial for advancing sustainable development. Both parties are interested in attaining sustainable development. Doing the right thing for the environment may open new business markets, enhance their reputation with stakeholders, and help them stand out with their offerings (Gupta & Srivastava, 2021). To summarize, there is a good correlation between sustainable development and both general and social entrepreneurship. Determining the variables influencing both forms of entrepreneurship is intriguing because of this.

Overview of Social Entrepreneurship and Sustainability

Social entrepreneurship is a term that denotes a business model by a non-governmental organisation focused on addressing social challenges and their needs, using market-oriented approaches and methods or processes of generating income that would help achieve stability in society (Iyortsuun, 2016). According to the School of Social Innovation, social entrepreneurship involves creativity in promoting change in order to solve certain social issues. It can be noted here that it gives more importance to social outcome over personal income-earning ability. As defined by Arejiogbe *et al.* (2023), social entrepreneurship is an organisation that focuses on carrying out its mission to positively affect society rather than striving to make profits. Social entrepreneurship involves recognising opportunities that exist within society where a specific need is not fulfilled and using solution-based approaches to address these needs. Social entrepreneurship is gradually receiving a favourable hearing in Nigeria as a tool that can solve different problems facing the society today, such as poverty, unemployment, health care, education, amongst others and environmental pollution. According to Ogbari, Ingomowei, and Ohanyelu (2023), the combined approaches of a nonprofit organisation coupled with a business model market have made social entrepreneurs in Nigeria search for sustainable solutions to some of the most difficult challenges facing the country.

According to Delgado *et al.* (2024), economic sustainability refers to sustainable economic growth for development without compromising the social, environmental or cultural structures of the society. Social sustainability refers to the provision of basic needs for all the members of a given community. Some of the greatest challenges affecting Africa today are: poverty, poor

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health infrastructure and education system, environmental problems and poor economic status (Iyortsuun, 2016). Sustainability needs to be incorporated into the social fabric to overcome the long-term development tendencies. Social entrepreneurs are well placed to advocate for sustainable development through innovations for tackling any social and ecological challenge (Iyortsuun, 2016). In the opinion of Ogbari et al. (2023), agriculture that employs many people in Africa is another area in which social entrepreneurship fosters sustainability. Social enterprises are using technology in production, processing, marketing, and value addition, too. For instance, there exist some companies like Farmcrowdy, which connect investors to smallholder farmers who are supplied with capital and other requirements to increase production. Indeed it is clear that these enterprises enhance food availability and access, income, rural livelihoods, and sustainability of agricultural systems. As for now, Nigeria also sustains social entrepreneurship and political and Policy measures, as well as non-governmental and International collaborations in terms of preserving the environment for social entrepreneurship (Lubberink, 2020).

Kickul, Gundry, Mitra and Berçot (2018) found that social entrepreneurs are coming up with solutions in the education sector that will help to enhance literacy and learning rates. Odeyemi (2023) highlighted this by explaining that through organisations such as Andela, young Nigerians are being trained in software development and linking up with world tech firms on the skill deficient areas and employment needs. Thus, on improving human capital and supporting further education these enterprises affect economic sustainable development as well as poverty and inequalities reduction (Iyortsuun 2016). They assist in the creation of efficiency in a knowledge-based economy, which is crucial for sustainable national development. These efforts are supported by the activities of NGOs and international organisations that contribute more necessary resources and skills to advance social inventions (Ogbari et al., 2023; Gupta et al., 2015; Kickul et al., 2018).

Poverty Reduction and Inequality Intervention in Emerging Economies

To understand the relationship between income inequality and growth-poverty, it is essential to provide insights into how the rapid growth of developing countries has impacted human development, particularly through poverty reduction (Fosu, 2017; World Bank, 2006). Adejuwon and Tijani (2012) noted that even though all the countries grew at the same rate, their risks of achieving the first MDG — to halve poverty by 2015 — had been dissimilar. This is because inequality affects the transformation from growth to poverty reduction rather than the widely accepted growth rate of 7% per Year for GDP growth.

Mass poverty has been acknowledged in recent decades as a significant obstacle to sustained economic growth as well as something that is morally and politically unacceptable. Policies aimed at reducing poverty are now possible because of growing public awareness of the issue and improvements in countries' economic capacities to deal with issues of inequality and chronic poverty (Agri, Nanwul & Acha, 2017; Manjon et al., 2022). Fosu (2017) stated that countries in the early stages of development have more equitable income distributions since most economic agents are impoverished and the economies are defined by generalized poverty. World Bank (2006) defines poverty using poverty lines, which estimate the costs of goods and services required to meet basic subsistence needs (Williams & Kedir, 2019). Thus, the poor are individuals whose incomes fall within or below particular poverty levels. The most widely recognised worldwide poverty line is \$1.90 per day.

Due to poor economic foundations and sluggish progress, Nigeria's inflation increased to a 24-year high of 31.7% in February 2024 (World Bank 2024), leaving millions impoverished. Nigeria has the largest population and economy in Africa, but it offers the majority of its citizens few opportunities. Consequently, human capital index describing Nigeria's child born in 2020 is estimated by the seventh rank lowest to be only 36% productive as workers if they receive proper health care services and education (Fosu, 2017). Since there are not enough job or entrepreneurship opportunities for Nigeria's 3.5 million new workers, many leave the country for better opportunities elsewhere. Nigeria, with a predicted poverty rate of 38.9% in 2023, has the second-largest poor population, following India, with approximately 87 million people living in poverty (Hidalgo, Monticelli, and Vargas, 2024; Manjon et al., 2022).

Research Methods

The guideline adopted in this study was the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA). The review is strengthened by compliance with criteria for and practices for undertaking systematic reviews: development of comprehensive search terms and strategy, explicit eligibility criteria for studies and comprehensive quality assessment of studies that meet inclusion criteria. There are five electronic databases, Journal articles, the grey literature, and websites as the sources of the papers over a certain period. Keywords and search terms related to social entrepreneurship, poverty reduction, inequality, emerging economies, and impact evaluation are used to retrieve relevant literature comprehensively. Inclusion criteria are defined based on the relevance of studies to the research question, focusing on empirical research and systematic reviews that examine the efficacy of social entrepreneurship interventions in addressing poverty and inequality in emerging economies. This study describes social entrepreneurship initiatives' objectives, methodologies, outcomes, and impact evaluation measures. Data extraction and synthesis involve systematically reviewing and summarizing key findings from included studies, focusing on the effectiveness of social entrepreneurship interventions in reducing poverty and inequality and the contextual factors influencing their success or failure. Data synthesis employed thematic analysis to identify common themes, patterns, and discrepancies across studies, providing insights into the overall efficacy of social entrepreneurship in addressing socioeconomic challenges in emerging economies. The following will provide an account of the search strategy, eligibility criteria for studies included, data collection, method of assessing quality of evidence and that of synthesising data.

Search Strategy

According to the PRISMA guidelines for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses, the literature was searched using the following sources: Google Scholar, ResearchGate, Scopus, and ScienceDirect, within a standard 15-year time frame from 2009 to 2024.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Studies were included if they met the following criteria:

- Relate to social entrepreneurship, poverty and inequality, sustainability, and social entrepreneurship initiatives.
- Published between 2009 and 2024
- Easy access to the full body of the Article

Some of the reasons for exclusion included if the study met any of the following characteristics:

- Not available in the English Language
- The article was older than 15 years
- Did not include the keywords of social entrepreneurship, poverty and inequality, sustainability, and social entrepreneurship initiatives

Data Extraction

The articles were also examined separately by the researchers to extract the relevant data. The following information was obtained from each of the Study Includes;

- Author
- Year of publication
- Title of publication
- Definition of concepts
- Theories
- Results
- Conclusion

Figure 1 PRISMA Guidelines

Source: Researcher PRISMA Model

Results and Discussion of Findings

The Role of Social Entrepreneurship in Poverty and Inequality Reduction

In the view of Kamaludin, Xavier, and Amin (2024) social entrepreneurship is defined as the development and growth of solutions to societal problems. Such players in the industry work hand in hand with society to understand their needs and come up with suitable value proposals that address the appropriate causes. In addressing poverty and inequality challenges, social entrepreneurs help identify Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 1 and 10) to demonstrate that economic development can be sustainable and reduce inequalities. Those social entrepreneurs who intended to pursue employment generation and economic development to address poverty and unfairness in Nigeria did so through the formation of more social businesses in the country, such as Jobberman. Social entrepreneurs also highlighted skills development programmes for individuals.

The study revealed that social enterprises (SEs) have been instrumental in driving the growth of the Nigerian economy by establishing firms that address some of the challenges, including unemployment, as noted by Hidalgo et al. (2024), Ogbari et al. (2024), and Arejiogbe et al. (2023). Jobberman is a vast social enterprise developed to solve unemployment by connecting potential employees to their employers (Odeyemi, 2023). The platform also offers additional services, such as resume writing assistance for individuals who need to learn how to craft a professional resume. This platform has also designed skill development courses to help potential employees with different soft skills succeed in any organization.

Kickul and Lyons (2020) noted that social enterprises are effective in driving educational activities with skills development initiatives to aid boost individuals out of poverty. Social entrepreneurs can help individuals to obtain quality education and vocational training and can support career mentorship to make them employable and increase the economic future capital of a nation (Kickul & Lyons, 2020). The government, businesses, and individuals in a community can engage a social entrepreneur to deal with the problems of flooding which is one of the root causes of poverty due to displacement of communities, loss of homes and income sources through loss of crops and other properties, disruption of agriculture (Kamaludin et al., 2024). Hidalgo *et al.* (2024) opined that the rising phenomenon of social entrepreneurship across the globe breaks poverty dramatically by offering job opportunities and improves social capital by incubating new social entrepreneurs, new employment chances, innovative ideas to develop the society, new models and so forth.

According to Manjon et al. (2022), social entrepreneurs build businesses with job creation objectives, especially targeting minorities. These enterprises concerned fields like agriculture, handicraft, tourism especially conservation related tourism and other income generating activities that support the economy as well as the natural environment.

Table 1: Initiatives of Social Enterprise in Nigeria and Their Roles

Social Enterprise	Founders	Initiatives	Location
Wecyclers	Bilikiss Adebisi-	Wecyclers promotes recycling and waste management, creating employment	Lagos

	Abiola	opportunities for low-income communities by incentivizing waste collection.	
The Roothub	Tony Onuk and Francis Onuk	The Roothub offers training, mentorship, and workspace for young entrepreneurs and startups, fostering innovation and reducing unemployment in the tech ecosystem.	Akwa Ibom State
Slum2School Africa	Otto Orondaam	Slum2School Africa provides education and healthcare support to children living in slum communities, addressing educational inequalities and improving access to quality education.	Lagos State
Andela Lagos	Jeremy Johnson, Iyinoluwa Aboyeji, Nadayar Enegesi, Brice Nkengsa, Ian Carnevale, and Christina Sass.	They leverage technology software developers in Nigeria by providing them with education and training, leading to self-skills and reduced unemployment.	Lagos
Tony Elumelu Foundation(TEF)	Tony O. Elumelu	This is an African charitable organisation that promotes entrepreneurship and provides support for entrepreneurs in finding ways to increase employment opportunities. Its major aim is to eliminate poverty on the African continent.	Africa
Education as a Vaccine (EVA)	Bisi Adeleye-Fayemi	EVA promotes sexual and reproductive health, gender equality, and youth empowerment through education, advocacy, and community engagement. It addresses social inequalities and improves health outcomes among adolescents and young people.	Abuja
Rural Farmers Hub	Muhammad Jibrin	Rural Farmers Hub leverages technology to connect rural farmers with markets, extension services, and financial resources, thereby increasing agricultural productivity, income	Kano State

generation, and job opportunities in rural areas.

Jobberman Ayodeji Jobberman is a leading online job portal Lagos
Adekunmi, that connects job seekers with State
Olalekan employers, helping to reduce
Olude, and unemployment by facilitating job
Opeyemi matches and providing career
Awoyemi development resources and training
programs.

Barriers Limiting the Effectiveness of Social Entrepreneurship in Eradicating Poverty and Inequality

While the concept of social entrepreneurship offers significant opportunities to solve the problems of poverty and inequality, there are several crucial obstacles to achieving maximum results. However, more government aid is needed to enable social entrepreneurs to fulfil their mission of addressing social problems (Arejiogbe et al., 2023). While many policies and legal measures exist to support the entrepreneurial activities of profit firms, social entrepreneurs still enjoy little legal and governmental protection.

According to the findings, Manjon et al. (2022) stated that limited access to financial and human resources is another barrier limiting the effectiveness of social entrepreneurship in reducing poverty and inequality. Traditional funding models often need to pay more attention to ventures with a social focus, making it hard for social entrepreneurs to secure the necessary capital to scale their initiatives (Alao & Alao, 2021; Arejiogbe et al., 2023). According to Iyortsuun (2016), the absence of workforce, professional staff and proper policies incapacitates the development and enforcement of proper standard solutions. Such a vacuum arises from the fact that conventional investors put more emphasis on financial interventions than social impacts, according to Kamaludin et al. (2024). Lubberink (2020) has also pointed out that a lot of social companies heavily depend on grants and contributions that sometimes are small, unpredictable and inadequate for long-term growth. Such a financial environment might inhibit the growth of social businesses' impact and contribute to the restriction of user penetration. Existing studies show that social enterprises require assistance in obtaining sufficient funding (Ogbari et al. 2023). Okebiorun and Ige's (2024) review of the current literature shows that, unlike traditional business ventures, social enterprises are established for creating social value, not economic returns, so they are not attractive to traditional financiers. Gupta and Srivastava (2021) pointed out that this virtually creates tension, which complicates matters about the attainment of financial sustainability. However, funding from non-conventional sources normally goes with project-based and short-term projects. Hence, this is non-conventional and makes long-term planning almost impossible. This is alarming when it comes to the financial aspect, as it hinders the expansion of intensification, hence reaching out to more people.

In emerging economies, social and environmental problems are usually discussed in schools, giving youth awareness of what is happening in and around their communities and societies (Okebiorun & Ige, 2024). This awareness birthed what we now know as ENACTUS, where university students are taught to use innovative ways to solve global problems in communities. Another challenge or barrier limiting the effectiveness of social entrepreneurship in eradicating

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poverty and inequality is the need for more awareness. According to Alao and Alao (2021), social entrepreneurship should be added to schools' curricula, mainly at the tertiary level. Their study also stated that societal and community problems should be actively discussed among youth or students in class. When youths need to gain awareness of societal challenges, they cannot develop solutions to these problems. The educational system is the first place to create awareness of the problem of inequality and poverty in Nigeria.

It is also important to address the issue of culture and society when integrating the initiatives. Yeboua *et al.*, (2022) argue for the need to compare the differences and estimate the possible drawbacks that the newly considered area might encounter when implementing the given initiative with a new technology. Ignorance to the existing norms and cultures will, no doubt, hamper the success of the initiative to its eventual failure within a short period. According to Arejiogbe *et al.* (2023), the locally developed solution to the education problem is more preferred than that of external origin due to its appropriateness to the problem and challenge in question, which this research has also highlighted. Many of the developing countries from this study (African countries) have distinct cultures, languages and practices within different states and in different communities, let alone if the initiative is seeking to be spearheaded in a different country (Ogbari *et al.*, 2024). Lack of acceptance is one of the problems that social entrepreneurs encounter when presenting new ideas that do not conform to traditional standards of living and working. Unfortunately, according to Moline (2024), social entrepreneurship projects might encounter the following difficulty: The necessary community support to ensure the long-term eradication of poverty and create equal opportunities can be challenging to obtain without due consideration and proper integration of local cultures.

Conclusion

Through others' eyes, social entrepreneurs have the responsibility of decreasing the inequality in Nigeria since they are duty-bound to come up with strategic, proactive measures and interventions that would decrease inequalities. They establish companies and initiatives that value diversity, fair wages for workers, and access to tools for disadvantaged groups. As far as the models of functioning are concerned, the social enterprises consider anyone who is affected or involved in the process, and not only the financial shareholders, thereby promoting a balanced distribution of the profit. Social entrepreneurs can develop affordable, sustainable solutions that may be long-term and effective in addressing these needs, empowering communities for the future. Therefore, sustainable social entrepreneurship can transform emerging economies by improving transformation, bringing about practical change, and promoting social justice outcomes.

Recommendations, Suggestions for Further Studies

They explain how poverty and inequality are some of the worst vices that any emerging economy faces, which deny it the chance to grow and be prosperous. Social entrepreneurship has therefore been developed as a crucial method of solving such problems with sustainable and creative means. Social entrepreneurs wished to operate their organisations with sound business models, but with the deep passion and core purpose to effect change most effectively. Engaging governments, commercial businesses and communities is very important for both support and sustainability of the projects.

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A market-based approach that enables even small communities and individuals to devise solutions for overcoming the challenges that hinder the fulfilment of human needs is recommended, rather than relying on conventional philanthropy or government involvement. Through supporting economic growth, developing and enhancing education and promoting development, social enterprise can end the poverty and inequality traps.

The second of the key recommendations made is to enhance resource allocation towards education, particularly capacity building. Through skills development and training, social enterprises can improve the productivity of their human capital, thereby enhancing their results. Last, mainstreaming of environmental sustainability in poverty reduction initiatives guarantees sustainable economic growth and development. These include supporting organic farming, supporting power generation from renewable sources and policies that favour the conservation of natural resources and control of pollution.

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Author Contributions

Conceptualization, A.B.A; methodology, I.P.S; validation, O.E.M; formal analysis, I.P.S; investigation, I.P.S; resources, A.B.A; writing—original draft preparation, I.P.S; writing—review and editing, I.P.S; visualization, O.E.M.; supervision, O.E.M.; project administration, A.B.A. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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